

LV-UA NEW MEDIA DPP

Version 1

Description

Research project "War Through the Lens of New Media: Documentation Methods and Challenges in the Post-Digital Era" involves a qualitative study of the latest methods and forms of documenting the events of Russia's war against Ukraine as demonstrated by contemporary media practices.

The goal of the project is to analyze and research technologies and formats of new media that cover the events of Russia's full-scale aggression, with the aim of effectively integrating these insights into educational programs to enhance media literacy and critical thinking, and to improve the training of specialists who use new media for documenting and analyzing war events.

The project is conducted through Latvian-Ukrainian Joint Program of Scientific and Technological Cooperation.

Funder

The Latvian Council of Science
and the Ministry of Education

Grant

The project is conducted
through Latvian-Ukrainian Joint

and Science of Ukraine

Program of Scientific and
Technological Cooperation.

Researchers

Yuliia Kovalenko (0000-0001-6694-8329), Natalia Korzhyk (0000-0002-0305-2864), Yuliia Litynska (0000-0001-8368-8207), Maksym Demydenko (0000-0001-8021-2641), Maija Spurina (0000-0002-6978-1322), Eva Marhilevica

Organizations

Latvian Academy of Culture, Kharkiv State Academy of Culture

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [LV-UA NEW MEDIA DPP](#)

Description:

Research project "War Through the Lens of New Media: Documentation Methods and Challenges in the Post-Digital Era" involves a qualitative study of the latest methods and forms of documenting the events of Russia's war against Ukraine as demonstrated by contemporary media practices.

The goal of the project is to analyze and research technologies and formats of new media that cover the events of Russia's full-scale aggression, with the aim of effectively integrating these insights into educational programs to enhance media literacy and critical thinking, and to improve the training of specialists who use new media for documenting and analyzing war events.

The project is conducted through Latvian-Ukrainian Joint Program of Scientific and Technological Cooperation.

Researchers:

[Yuliia Kovalenko \(0000-0001-6694-8329\)](#)

[Natalia Korzhyk \(0000-0002-0305-2864\)](#)

[Yuliia Litynska \(0000-0001-8368-8207\)](#)

[Maksym Demydenko \(0000-0001-8021-2641\)](#)

[Maija Spurina \(0000-0002-6978-1322\)](#)

[Eva Marhilevica](#)

Organizations:

[Latvian Academy of Culture](#)

[Kharkiv State Academy of Culture](#)

Contact: [Spuriņa Maija \(maiija.spurina@lka.edu.lv\)](mailto:maiija.spurina@lka.edu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: The Latvian Council of Science and the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine

Grants: The project is conducted through Latvian-Ukrainian Joint Program of Scientific and Technological Cooperation.

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Audiovisual testimonies of Russian-Ukrainian War in digital media

War Through the Lens of New Media (...) involves a qualitative study of the latest methods and forms of documenting the events of Russia's war against Ukraine as demonstrated by contemporary media practices.

A collection of examples of how the Russian-Ukrainian war is audiovisually documented in media in Ukraine and Latvia. The dataset includes references to publicly available media resources and associated descriptive metadata. The examples were collected to represent a diversity of representations in terms of format, topic, and medium.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

A collection of examples of how the Russian–Ukrainian war is audiovisually documented in media in Ukraine and Latvia. The dataset includes references to publicly available media resources and associated descriptive metadata. The examples were collected to represent a diversity of representations in terms of format, topic, and medium.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The dataset may be useful for researchers in media and cultural studies, particularly in the context of war and conflict research.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

DataverseLV is a trusted national research data repository that ensures long-term preservation, controlled access options, and compliance with institutional and national research data management requirements.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The dataset is provided in XML format and can be accessed using standard XML viewers, text editors, or commonly used data analysis software.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The dataset is provided in an open, non-proprietary XML format, which is widely supported by software applications and allows for interoperability and recombination with other datasets.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Data processing and management will be covered by the research project funding.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data management will be overseen by the lead researcher and carried out by the project team, in accordance with institutional research data management guidelines.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Data processing and management will be covered by the research project funding.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

During data collection and processing, the data will be stored on the institution's OneDrive cloud server, which provides various security measures, including version control and access control. Access to the data will be granted only to the researchers involved in the project.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

